

ENABLING FINANCIAL INCLUSIVITY: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN THE ADOPTION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF QR PH IN VALENZUELA CITY

Junel S. Barquilla¹, Mark Josua B. Dela Rosa²,
Cleo Andrew M. Merejilla³, Dan Chester G. Ronda⁴,
Marie Chrese S.A. Villaruel⁵,
Dr. John A. Cabaddu⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5}Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela, Student, College of Public Administration and Governance, Valenzuela City, Philippines.

⁶Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela, Faculty, College of Public Administration and Governance, Valenzuela City, Philippines.

ABSTRACT

The Philippines firmly recognized the importance of digitalization as an instigating factor in enabling greater financial inclusivity and addressing the persisting socio-economic disparity between social classes. Thus, due to the recent empirical results indicating a significant correlation between the use of digital payment methods and financial inclusivity, various government instrumentalities in the Philippines committed to formulating and implementing initiatives to digitalize payment systems in the country. Implementing the National QR Code Standard (QR Ph) has become one of the most crucial steps in the nation's pursuit of financial inclusiveness. However, the goal of realizing greater financial inclusivity with the help of QR Ph remained a considerably challenging task due to the existing issues and challenges that hindered its full adoption and implementation. Despite the positive impact on financial inclusivity, numerous market vendors remained non-participants in the QR Ph initiative. Therefore, this study analyzed the current status of QR Ph implementation and its impact on the working conditions of market vendors. Moreover, it also sought to concretely identify and assess the hindrances that impeded the complete adoption and implementation of QR Ph from the perspectives of both the market vendors and policy implementers within Valenzuela City. The importance of this study lay in its objective to produce a robust network of empirical insights on the discourse regarding the QR Ph implementation. In addition, the findings of this study resulted in the extraction of relevant data with significant implications that aided the researchers in formulating policy enhancement recommendations to strengthen and empower the utilization of QR Ph in grassroots communities and ultimately contributed as an enabling factor in instigating greater financial inclusivity in Valenzuela City.

Keywords: Digital Payment, Financial Inclusivity, Market Vendors, QR Ph, Valenzuela City

INTRODUCTION

The Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic significantly impacted people's daily lives, jobs, and the global economy. The economic burden on the health system, the closing of businesses, and the lockdown created lasting problems (Sharma, 2020). As a solution, nations attempted to enhance financial

inclusion to boost economic recovery. Financial inclusion referred to providing people and companies with access to services related to financial transactions, such as credit, among others, which were affordable. By promoting digital transactions that were adopted, this goal was more easily achieved, as it largely led to increased usage rates within this sector (World Bank, 2022). In many developing nations, traditional banking was often out of reach for a significant portion of the population, leading to financial exclusion and socio-economic disadvantages. One of the essential aspects of financial inclusion was the use of digital payments, which significantly improved access to financial services. Digital payments were transactions made using online or electronic methods without physical cash exchange, involving the transfer of money from one payment account to another through digital devices such as mobile phones, computers, credit cards, debit cards, or prepaid cards (Khaitan, 2024). While digital payments offered numerous benefits, including the elimination of cash-related problems and reduced costs of payment systems, they also posed challenges, such as vulnerability to hacking and privacy invasions. Despite these challenges, digital payments were expected to play an increasingly important role in financial technology.

The term financial inclusion in the Philippines referred to a condition whereby all people could access different financial products and services easily. While there had been advancements, many Filipinos were still unable to access such important financial services. The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) had introduced the National Strategy on Financial Inclusion 2022-2028 to change this. In the Philippines, the Covid-19 pandemic had accelerated the uptake of electronic money payments. Consequently, QR Ph, which was launched by BSP, helped consumers achieve greater utilization of digital payment services. According to Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP), the QR Ph allowed people to use any digital payment of their choice through the interoperability feature of QR Ph payments, aligning with the United Nations principle on the responsible use of digital payments. In the Philippines, the COVID-19 pandemic led to increased use of digital payments. Filipinos increasingly embraced mobile wallets and card payments for online shopping, a trend that persisted even as pandemic restrictions eased. Users subsequently saw cashless transactions as more secure and convenient. According to records of 2020, digital financial transactions through mobile wallets drew an impressive figure of about 25 million Filipinos, and the top mobile wallets were GCash together with Maya. QR code-based payments also gained prominence as convenient alternatives in recent times (Chandra, 2024).

The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) launched the quick response (QR) code, the QR Ph Program, in 2019. The Philippine Government viewed this as an opportunity to utilize digital payment systems for accelerated business recovery as the country recovered from the COVID-19 pandemic. Becoming a digital nation became imperative due to population growth and demand (Kraus et al., 2021). The pandemic hastened this digital transformation (Priyono et al., 2020), with more frequent use of digital payments driven by the pandemic (BSP, 2021).

The implementation of QR Ph in Valenzuela City marked a significant step forward. Recent legislation, Ordinance No. 1101, which was approved on May 29, 2023, was implemented with the purpose of boosting small businesses in the area. Ordinance No. 1101, enacted on May 29, 2023, aimed to bolster local commerce. However, it contrasted with the Joint Memorandum Circular No. 1 issued by the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) and BSP in June 2022, highlighting a significant postponement in its full execution. Despite this postponement, the advent of digitalization and the growing preference for cashless transactions presented substantial opportunities. By using QR Ph, Valenzuela markets could potentially make operations more efficient, enhance user satisfaction, and promote economic expansion, thereby boosting growth. With digital transactions, traders could make acquisitions promptly and securely. According to Singh et al. (2017), digital payments made transactions fast and safe, reduced the burden of payment processing, and minimized errors. Quicker processing of transactions and decreased time spent on settling them had a positive effect on cash flow,

enabling businesses to manage their funds more easily. Digital payments also enhanced the effectiveness of government payments, subsidies, and tax collection systems.

Although there were many benefits, problems connected to Valenzuela City's QR Ph adoption and implementation resulted in delays, possibly bringing about negative repercussions for society and the market. Thus, addressing these problems was critical to ensure that QR Ph was adopted and used effectively within Valenzuela City to help build a robust and all-encompassing digital economy. Promoting financial inclusion and increasing economic growth in the city requires understanding and tackling these challenges.

The study aimed to identify the issues and challenges of adopting QR Ph in Valenzuela City to enhance financial inclusivity. It sought to analyze QR Ph's current status and its impact on the working conditions of market vendors, particularly in Polo Public Market and Marulas Public Market, as well as identify and assess the hindrances impeding its full adoption and implementation from the perspectives of both market vendors and policy implementers within Valenzuela City. The findings of this study provided empirical insights into QR Ph implementation and offered recommendations for policy enhancements to strengthen and empower the utilization of QR Ph in grassroots communities, ultimately contributing to greater financial inclusivity in Valenzuela City.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized a Mixed Method approach to identify and analyze the existing issues and challenges in the adoption and implementation of QR Ph (Quick Response Payment) in Valenzuela City by answering the following research questions: (1) What was the current status of QR Ph in Valenzuela City? (2) What were the challenges faced by the local government and market vendors in the implementation of QR Ph and its impact on achieving financial inclusivity in Valenzuela City? (3) Was there a significant relationship between the perception of local government and market vendors in the implementation of QR Ph in Valenzuela City? (4) What program plan could be developed to strengthen the implementation of QR Ph?

The indicated research questions were answered through a triangulation approach, combining research tools that facilitated both qualitative and quantitative approaches, such as primary and secondary data, surveys, and interviews, to extract an in-depth, accurate, and robust network of knowledge. The participants included in this study were considered key individuals in the following selected study sites: (1) Polo Public Market, (2) Marulas Public Market, and (3) the Local Economic Development and Investment Promotion Office (LEDIPO).

Recognizing the importance of comparative analysis as the primary basis for establishing validity, the researchers utilized survey questionnaires to gather relevant insights from 186 market vendors operating under Polo Public Market and 107 market vendors under Marulas Public Market. The determined sample size for each public market was methodically identified using the Yamane Formula. Moreover, the respondents for each public market were categorized into two clusters determined by their participation in the QR Ph initiative. Cluster 1 included market vendors who were classified as QR Ph participants. In contrast, Cluster 2 participants consisted of market vendors who were classified as non-QR Ph participants.

To aid the process of understanding and examining the data extracted from the respondents, the researchers utilized descriptive quantitative analysis and descriptive qualitative analysis to identify and summarize the current status of the implementation of QR Ph and its effectiveness among market vendors. In addition, thematic analysis was also used to systematically analyze the dataset and uncover the underlying themes and patterns present in the participants' responses.

To further obtain a deeper level of understanding regarding the issues at hand, the researchers also sought insights from policy implementers and other experts through interviews. The gathered information extracted from the Key Informants (KIs) was examined by identifying and evaluating particular concepts, trends, and themes found within their responses using content analysis. To achieve the study's aim of effectively pursuing policy enhancement, relevant data was gathered from multiple sources to produce a reliable network of information and was analyzed using appropriate data analysis tools to ensure validity and accuracy in interpreting the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to analyze the status of QR Ph implementation and its impact on the working conditions of market vendors. Moreover, it also sought to concretely identify and assess the hindrances that impeded the complete adoption and implementation of QR Ph from the perspectives of both the market vendors and policy implementers within Valenzuela City. Results from various studies were revealed and categorized in accordance with the adoption and implementation of digital payments.

Digital Payments as a tool for Digital Governance

The shift to digital payments had been one of the most significant changes in modern governance, reshaping how the public sector interacted with individuals and businesses. As digital technology continued to evolve, governments worldwide leveraged digital payment systems to enhance efficiency, transparency, and financial inclusivity.

The COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst for the rapid acceptance of digital payment methods, promoted digital transformation within industries and government agencies (Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas, 2021). With the progression of digital services, governments continued to intertwine electronic payment platforms such as e-wallets and mobile money, hence enabled citizens to transact, save, and pay with extra ease. Such electronic payment platforms' work was most pronounced in developing nations where traditional banking infrastructure was often underdeveloped (World Bank, 2019).

Security remained a primary concern in digital payments. While digital transactions were designed to be more secure than traditional cash-based payments, they were still vulnerable to hacking, fraud, and cyberattacks. The government had a critical role in regulating the digital payment ecosystems to attain these benefits and developed trust in users (Bank for International Settlements, 2023). According to the Bank for International Settlements (2023), digital fraud had become an operational risk with institutions as cybercriminals tended to obtain unauthorized access to banking credentials, and the need for cybersecurity regulations was greater than ever (Gillis, 2023).

In addition, digital payment systems have shown the effectiveness of improving governance efficiency. It was noted that India's Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) method had reduced the leakage of funds, as direct subsidies and welfare payments were deposited in citizens' bank accounts (Joy, 2018). Likewise, Estonia had already applied the use of e-government technologies in improving financial transparency, thus giving citizens real-time tracking of government transactions and building up their trust (Mechitov et al., 2021).

The Philippines had taken significant steps toward digital financial inclusion. The Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) introduced the Digital Payments Transformation Roadmap as part of the promotion for digital transactions and financial services across all sectors (Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas, 2021). The country's adoption of QR Ph, a standardized QR code payment system, reflected this commitment to fostering a cashless economy while ensuring that financial services remained accessible to all.

Digital governance encompassed a larger scope than just public services and financial transactions from the web; digital payments were a crucial tool in enabling more efficient, transparent, and inclusive governance. Strong regulatory frameworks in favor of digital payments, along with strong technological infrastructure and continuous public awareness programs for popularizing the use of such payments, were the determinants of their success in governance (Oliveira et al., 2019).

Concept of Financial Inclusivity

Financial inclusion aims to provide equal access to financial services, enhancing financial stability, health, and education opportunities (Veena M., 2024). Lal (2021) emphasizes that socio-economic and demographic factors—such as age, gender, and household size—shape financial inclusion, highlighting the importance of targeted interventions.

The study on QR Ph adoption in Valenzuela City's public markets supports this, showing that age plays a crucial role in digital payment adoption. Younger vendors (31-40 years old) are more receptive to QR Ph, likely due to greater tech familiarity, while older vendors (41-60 years old) struggle with digital literacy barriers, slowing adoption. Interestingly, gender does not significantly affect adoption rates, suggesting that both male and female vendors have similar levels of access and willingness to adopt QR Ph.

Additionally, factors such as years of residency, market experience, and income levels influence openness to digital transactions. Vendors with more experience and stable incomes may feel less urgency to shift to digital payments, whereas newer vendors might see QR Ph as an opportunity to attract customers. These insights highlight the need for tailored financial inclusion strategies, such as digital literacy programs and incentives, to bridge the digital divide and ensure accessibility for all market vendors.

Linking Digital Payments to Financial Inclusivity

Market vendors and policy implementers both recognize QR Ph as a convenient and modern payment method, but their perspectives differ in key areas. Vendors acknowledge its benefits, such as faster transactions and increased customer convenience, yet they highlight major barriers, including limited digital literacy, unstable internet connections, and frequent system downtimes. Some vendors, particularly older ones, struggle with the transition to digital payments, while others hesitate due to concerns over fraud and transaction failures.

Policy implementers, on the other hand, emphasize the necessity of QR Ph for economic growth and modernization. They recognize the challenges vendors face but believe the long-term benefits outweigh the difficulties. For them, digital payments streamline transactions, reduce reliance on cash, and promote financial inclusivity. However, they acknowledge that adoption remains uneven, particularly among marginalized groups who lack access to the necessary technology and financial services.

The challenges surrounding QR Ph adoption also differ in focus. Vendors see system reliability and consumer hesitancy as the primary obstacles, while policy implementers stress the need for greater public awareness, training, and infrastructure improvements. Despite these issues, both groups agree that QR Ph has the potential to enhance financial inclusivity by making transactions more accessible and increasing customer reach. However, full adoption requires stronger government support, improved digital education, and better technological infrastructure to ensure that all sectors of society can benefit from the transition to cashless payments.

Integrating Digital Payments into Policy Adoption and Implementation

As the world adapts to the growing need for digital payments, the United Nations – Better Than Cash Alliance introduced the United Nations Principles for Responsible Digital Payments, emphasizing the responsible development of new technologies, a user-centered approach, and actionable recommendations for lasting positive change. These principles clarify the roles and responsibilities of government institutions, banks, and payment service providers in fostering adoption of digital payment (Giovanis et al., 2019). Aligned with this global initiative, Valenzuela City implemented a policy framework to enhance the adoption of QR Ph, promoting seamless digital transactions. This study, based on its findings suggests that a key objective to improve coordination among local and national agencies, financial service providers, businesses, and stakeholders is necessary to create an inclusive digital payment ecosystem. Grounded in Valenzuela City Ordinance No. 1101, series of 2023, which supports the Paleng-QR Code QR Ph Program of the DILG and BSP, the framework encouraged businesses to embrace digital transactions. However, challenges such as limited technological infrastructure and vendor support hindered full implementation. Addressing these issues requires strategic monitoring, investment in technological infrastructure, and collaboration among stakeholders. Overcoming these barriers was essential in fostering financial inclusivity and resilience. Ultimately, this framework positioned Valenzuela as a model city for integrating digital payments into sustainable urban development.

Challenges in integrating digital payments into policy adoption and implementation.

The adoption of QR Ph in Valenzuela City presents both technical and human-related challenges, reflecting the diverse experiences of market vendors and policy implementers. Respondents from Marulas Public Market emphasized system-based issues, particularly the frequent downtime and maintenance problems of mobile payment platforms like GCash. One vendor noted that transactions often failed due to the app going offline, causing inconvenience for both sellers and buyers. This finding aligns with Pueblos & Timoteo Jr. (2023), who identified technical difficulties as a major barrier for micro and small entrepreneurs in adopting digital payments.

In contrast, a vendor from Polo Public Market argued that the primary issue was not the system itself but people's willingness and ability to use it. He asserted that while the system was functional, many vendors lacked digital literacy or resisted the shift to cashless transactions. This perspective was echoed by a policy implementer from LEDIPO, who pointed out that some business owners were unfamiliar with mobile transactions or hesitant due to concerns about fraud and scams. Indeed, digital fraud remains a significant challenge in the Philippines, with cybercriminals frequently targeting users of digital payment platforms (Statista, 2023). Additionally, an LEDIPO officer highlighted the role of infrastructure in adoption challenges, particularly unreliable internet connectivity. Without stable internet access, even vendors willing to adopt QR Ph face difficulties in completing transactions. This aligns with global discussions on digital payment adoption, where financial inclusion is hindered not only by security risks and regulatory challenges (Chen, 2019) but also by gaps in digital access.

Despite these challenges, both vendors and policy implementers recognize the potential benefits of QR Ph in promoting financial inclusivity. By offering a more convenient and secure payment option, digital transactions can expand customer reach and improve business operations. However, achieving full adoption requires a multi-faceted approach—enhancing system reliability, strengthening digital literacy, improving cybersecurity measures, and expanding internet infrastructure. The Philippines' efforts to integrate digital payments reflect a broader global trend toward financial inclusion, underscoring the need for continuous policy improvements and public awareness campaigns.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There are several new findings that emerged in the study regarding the application and impact that QR Ph has brought to market vendors in Valenzuela City with much focus placed on the responsibility of promoting the uptake of financial services and digital payments. It emphasizes the importance of the sphere of digital payments as the component of digital government in which these services define the relations between citizens, businessmen, and the state. Mobile payments for instance in the form of e-wallets impacted merchants through expanding their sales reach and financial inclusion for both digitally included and excluded across global commerce especially in the developing world. Financial inclusion is therefore a methodology of the right supply of the appropriate financial services and products that facilitates the economic aspect in a particular society. The study also supports the view that financial literacy and inclusion programs should be mutually the key initiatives towards the achievement of a common goal of reducing service deficiencies and enhancing economic status. Concerning the financial exclusion, central banks' transition to digital payment systems can be essential since it seeks to open financial services, including the ability to provide services to vulnerable groups in society despite factors such as accessibility and availability of information. Technological change, growth on the internet and smartphone navigation, and shifting consumer behavior are all factors influencing the adoption of digital payments in policy adoption and implementation; the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) has enhanced digital services. However, there are issues like cybercrime, online scam, and lack of user awareness which are still prevalent that require the use of strict measures on how digital payment systems will be implemented.

The established results correlate with the trends identified worldwide in the field of digital governance and financial literacy noting that digital payments are a significant factor in the progression of the economic spectrum. Like other countries, the Philippines acknowledges the partnerships of central banks and government policies when it comes to the development of digitized financial services. Thus, the main obstacles identified concerning digital payments correspond to the literature concerned with emerging markets, stating that the lack of financial literacy and awareness is the most crucial factor contributing to the high levels of non-adoption. This should form the basis for further studies on digital payment systems in other regions and sectors to get a complete picture of the hurdles as well as the advantages. This information would provide a comparative analysis of different countries' practices and ideas on how to improve the financial inclusion of those members of society that are excluded from economic activity. Further, it would be useful to examine the negative or positive influence of digital payments on economic development and the existence of any latent lengthy effects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researchers are deeply grateful to their research advisor, Dr. John A. Cabaddu, for his invaluable mentorship and support. Their heartfelt appreciation goes to their respective family and friends for their unwavering encouragement, especially during challenging times. Lastly, the researchers extend their gratitude to all the participants whose insights and contributions enriched this study.

REFERENCES

- Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas. (2021). National strategy for financial inclusion 2022-2028. Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas – Inclusive Finance. <https://www.bsp.gov.ph/Pages/InclusiveFinance/NSFI-2022-2028.pdf>
- Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas. (2021). State of digital payments in the Philippines – Highlights Report (2021 edition). United Nations Capital Development Fund (UNCDF). Manila, Philippines. https://www.bsp.gov.ph/PaymentAndSettlement/2021_State_of_Digital_Payments_in_the_Philippines.pdf

- Giovanis, et al. (2019). Adoption of mobile banking services: A comparative analysis of four competing theoretical models. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 37 (5) (2019), pp. 1165-1189. 10.1108/IJBM-08-2018-0200
- Joy, J. (2018, August). A critical analysis of direct benefit transfer in India. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331861666_A_critical_analysis_of_direct_benefit_transfer_in_India
- Khaitan, P. (2024, February 14). What is digital payment and how does it work? *Forbes Advisor INDIA*. <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/in/banking/what-is-a-digital-payment-and-how-does-it-work/>
- Kraus, S., Jones, P., Kailer, N., Weinmann, A., Chaparro-Banegas, N., & Roig-Tierno, N. (2021). Digital Transformation: An Overview of the Current State of the Art of Research. *Sage Open*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211047576>
- Lal, T. (2021). Impact of financial inclusion on economic development of marginalized communities through the mediation of social and economic empowerment. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 48(12), 1768–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijse-12-2020-0830>
- Medalla, F. M. (2022, December 1). Digital Payments Transformation: The Key to Financial Inclusion. *Banko Sentral ng Pilipinas*. <https://www.bsp.gov.ph/SitePages/MediaAndResearch/SpeechesDisp.aspx?ItemId=994>
- Moin, A., Priyono, A., & Putri, V. O. (2020, October 03). Identifying digital transformation paths in the business model of SMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic. *MDPI*. <https://www.mdpi.com/2199-8531/6/4/104>
- Pueblos, K. J., & Timoteo Jr., E. (2023). Impact of E-Payment Platforms Among Selected Micro-Entrepreneurs in Taguig City: Determinants for Enhanced Guidelines in Collection and Disbursement Process. *Indonesian Journal of Business Analytics*, 3(4), 1401-1424. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijba.v3i4.4884>
- Sharma, R. R. (2020). Financial Inclusion and Economic Growth: Evidence-Based Research. *Vision*, 24(2), 139-139. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262920933503>
- Singh, S., & Rana, R. (2017, October 31). Study of consumer perception of digital payment mode. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*. <https://www.icommercecentral.com/open-access/study-of-consumer-perception-of-digital-payment-mode-php?aid=86419>
- Statista. (2023, December 21). Digital payments in the Philippines. <https://www.statista.com/topics/9799/digital-payments-in-the-philippines/#topicOverview>
- The World Bank. (2022, September 13). Financial Inclusion Overview. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/financialinclusion/overview>
- Tombini, A. (2023, October 29). Digital payments as a boon to financial inclusion. *Bank for International Settlements*. <https://www.bis.org/speeches/sp231029.htm>
- Veena, M. (2022). Conceptual Evolution of Financial Inclusion. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/CONCEPTUAL-EVOLUTION-OF-FINANCIAL-INCLUSION-Dr.Veena/bcae94f4a2b3232271ee940efe-255cfb420a751b>